

Photoelastic Analysis of the Effect of Residual Stress on the Deformation of Unidirectional Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastic at the Wedge Indentation

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the plane stress indentation of unidirectional glass fiber reinforced plastic materials using the photoelastic method. The both shapes of isochromatic and isoclinic pattern were strongly affected by the inclination angle of yarn to the side of rectangular specimen. There was found of the irregularity of photoelastic fringe between yarn part and matrix part. So that concerning the photoelastic analysis of wedge indentation, the residual stress distribution was assumed to explain the irregularity of this phenomena. The both results of theory and experiment were good agreement to each other.

NOMENCLATURE

$\sigma_r, \sigma_\theta, \tau_{r\theta}$ = the stresses in terms of polar coordinates
 $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}$ = the stresses in terms of rectangular coordinates
 $\sigma_0, \sigma_{0m}, \sigma_{0y}$ = the initial residual stresses in the specimen
 E_1, E_2 = Young's modulus
 G_{12} = the shear modulus
 ν_{12} = Poisson's ratio in fiber direction
 P = the concentrated load
 d = the width of specimen
 α = the inclination angle of yarn to the side of rectangular specimen

INTRODUCTION

On the wedge indentation for the glass fiber reinforced plastic materials, various failure patterns appearing near the tip of wedge indenters by changing the apex angle and the inclination angle of yarn to the side of rectangular specimen were defined using the white light [1,2,3]. However it is very difficult to get the stress or strain distribution in FRP under the wedge indenters.

On the other hand, the matrix of FRP itself has a photoelastic effect, so the photoelastic stress analysis was applied for the wedge indentation of FRP. A photoelastic analysis for the orthotropic composite materials was already studied, but these treatment are based on the macroscopic observation [4,5,6]. On studying the failure pattern between fiber and matrix of FRP, the photoelastic analysis based on the microscopic observation should be taken into consideration.

In this study the model of unidirectional glass fiber reinforced plastic specimen was applied to research the microscopic photoelastic experiment. And the initial residual stress being proportional to the volume content of glass fibers was used in the analytical treatment of photoelastic pattern.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Fig.1 shows the experimental apparatus. The indenting load to the specimen was given by the universal testing machine and the mercury lamp was used for the light source of this device. For the observation of photoelastic pattern, the green filter (5461Å) was used. The details of specimen and experimental procedure are shown in Table 1 and Fig.2.

Fig. 1 Experimental apparatus.
C: camera, S: light source, P: polaroid plate, Q: quarter wave plate, T: wedge indenting apparatus.

Fig. 2 Shape and size of test-piece.
a) specimen for wedge indentation,
b) specimen for photoelastic sensitivity,
c) specimen for material property.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULT

Fig.3 shows the isochromatic pattern obtained for the several inclination angle of yarn at the small indenting depth. The isochromatic patterns were not influenced by the shapes of wedges but were remarkably affected by the change of the inclination angle of yarn. The isochromatic lines spread in the tangential direction to the yarn from the tip of wedges and show the irregularity between yarn and matrix parts.

Fig.4 shows the map of isoclinic lines for the several inclination angles. The isoclinic lines were strongly affected by the direction of yarn as same as the case of isochromatic fringe and there is a singular point corresponding with the position of zero order's fringe in isochromatic fringes.

ANALYSIS

Two assumption were applied for the photoelastic analysis of the wedge indentation problems: One is to substitute the wedge indentation for the two dimensional plane stress model acting a normal concentrated force. The other is that the specimen has an initial residual stress which is caused by the difference of contraction between matrix and fibers in the production process of specimen and acts in the direction of a yarn.

Resin*	Unsaturated Polyester Polymal 6304, 6320F							
Yarn**	ECG-75-1/2 3.3S NA							
Volume content of fibers	0.85%							
Inclination angle of yarn	$\alpha = 0^\circ, 30^\circ, 60^\circ, 90^\circ$							
After cure	120°C, 2 h							
Size of specimen	48×70, d=6 mm							
Tool material	SKH-2, width b=6 mm							
Wedge angle	<table border="0"> <tr> <td rowspan="2">Symmetric wedge indenters</td> <td rowspan="2">}</td> <td>$2\theta = 30^\circ, 90^\circ, 120^\circ, 160^\circ$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Half wedge indenters</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> <td>$\theta = 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 80^\circ$</td> </tr> </table>	Symmetric wedge indenters	}	$2\theta = 30^\circ, 90^\circ, 120^\circ, 160^\circ$	Half wedge indenters			$\theta = 30^\circ, 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 80^\circ$
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Indenting depth	1 mm							
Velocity of indentation	0.1 mm/min							

* Takeda Chemical Industries Ltd.

** Nitto Boseki Co. Ltd.

Table 1 Detail of specimen and experimental procedure.

Fig. 3 Isochromatic lines(experimental results).
wedge angle: $20=120^\circ$, indenting depth: $t=0.1\text{mm}$.

Fig. 4 Map of isoclinic lines (experimental results).
wedge angle: $20=160^\circ$, indenting depth: $t=0.1\text{mm}$.

Although the volume content of glass fiber in the specimen is very little, the photoelastic sensitivity of this specimen depends on the direction of yarn. So the assumption of two ways were taken for the material property in the analysis: One is isotropic materials and the other is orthotropic ones.

1) For the isotropic materials

Let us consider a concentrated vertical force P acting on a horizontal straight boundary of an infinite plate as shown in Fig.5. Any element Q at a distance r from the point O acting load P is subjected to the next stresses.

$$\sigma_r = (-2P/\pi r d) \cos\theta, \quad \sigma_\theta = \tau_{r,\theta} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Moreover the residual stress acts upon the element Q . In terms of rectangular coordinates at the element Q , these stresses are obtained as follow:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= \sigma_r \cos^2\theta + \sigma_0 \sin^2\alpha \\ \sigma_y &= \sigma_r \sin^2\theta + \sigma_0 \cos^2\alpha \\ \tau_{x,y} &= (1/2)(\sigma_r \sin 2\theta - \sigma_0 \sin 2\alpha) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

From Eqs.2 the difference of principal stress at the element Q is given by the fomulas

$$\sigma_1 - \sigma_2 = \sqrt{(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 + 4\tau_{x,y}^2} = \sqrt{\sigma_r^2 + \sigma_0^2 - 2\sigma_r\sigma_0 \cos[2(\theta + \alpha)]} \quad (3)$$

The direction of principal stress (clockwork rotation) at the element Q is given by the fomulas

$$\varphi = \tan^{-1}\{2\tau_{x,y}/(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)\} = \tan^{-1}\{(\sigma_r \sin 2\theta - \sigma_0 \sin 2\alpha)/(\sigma_r \cos 2\theta - \sigma_0 \cos 2\alpha)\} \quad (4)$$

2) For the orthotropic materials

It is very difficult to solve the problem that a concentrated vertical force P acts on a horizontal straight boundary of an infinite orthotropic plate like as that of isotropic plate. So we used the Lekhnitskii's solution for the wedge shaped orthotropic body by a force applied at the apex [7]. The apex of wedge is the origin of coordinates and the direction of x -axis coincide with the principal direction (Fig.6). We also use polar coordinates and measure the polar angle θ

Fig. 5 Stress notation(isotropic materials).

σ_0 : residual stress, α : angle between Y -direction and direction of residual stress.

from the x-axis. The inclination angle of the edges to the x-axis are designated by ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 and the inclination angle of the force to the x-axis by w . The final formulas for stresses are

$$\sigma_r = \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{A \cos\theta + B \sin\theta}{L(\theta)}, \quad \sigma_\theta = \tau_{r\theta} = 0 \quad (5)$$

where

$$L(\theta) \equiv (1/S_{22}) \{S_{22} \sin^4\theta + (2S_{12} + S_{66}) \sin^2\theta \cos^2\theta + S_{11} \cos^4\theta\} \quad (6)$$

$$S_{11} = 1/E_1, \quad S_{12} = -\nu_{12}/E_1, \quad S_{22} = 1/E_2, \quad S_{66} = 1/G_{12}$$

Arbitrary constants A and B are determined from equilibrium conditions for a part of the wedge cut off by a circle of radius r starting from the apex. For these constants we obtain the following equations

$$\left. \begin{aligned} A \int_{-\phi_1}^{\phi_2} \frac{\cos^2\theta}{L(\theta)} d\theta + B \int_{-\phi_1}^{\phi_2} \frac{\cos\theta \sin\theta}{L(\theta)} d\theta &= -P \cos\alpha \\ A \int_{-\phi_1}^{\phi_2} \frac{\cos\theta \sin\theta}{L(\theta)} d\theta + B \int_{-\phi_1}^{\phi_2} \frac{\cos^2\theta}{L(\theta)} d\theta &= -P \sin\alpha \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

Now we defined as follow: $\phi_1 = \pi/2 - \alpha$, $\phi_2 = \pi/2 + \alpha$, $w = \pi - \alpha$. So that the wedge becomes the semi-infinite plate.

On the other hand, applying the photoelastic experiment for the anisotropic materials, it is permitted that the photoelastic fringes show the line of equal principal strain difference or the direction of principal strain instead of stress [8,9]. The discrepancy of the principal strains and the direction of principal strain are given as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} (\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2) &= \{[(S_{22} - S_{12})(\sigma_r \cos^2\theta + \sigma_\theta \sin^2\theta) - (S_{11} - S_{12})(\sigma_r \sin^2\theta + \sigma_\theta \cos^2\theta)]^2 \\ &+ (1/4) \cdot [S_{66}(\sigma_r \sin 2\theta - \sigma_\theta \sin 2\alpha)]^2\}^{1/2} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\varphi = (1/2) \tan^{-1}(\gamma_x / \epsilon_x - \epsilon_y)$$

$$= (1/2) \tan^{-1} \frac{(1/2) S_{66}(\sigma_r \sin 2\theta - \sigma_\theta \sin 2\alpha)}{[(S_{11} - S_{12})(\sigma_r \cos^2\theta + \sigma_\theta \sin^2\theta) - (S_{22} - S_{12})(\sigma_r \sin^2\theta + \sigma_\theta \cos^2\theta)]} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 6 Stress notation(orthotropic material).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The photoelastic sensitivity of glass fiber is quite low compare with that of resin(about 1/10 of resin), so it is assumed that glass fiber did not show the photoelastic effect. As the contraction of resin in the yarn is different from that of matrix which excepts the yarn parts, the photoelastical residual stress depends on the total light path length between yarn parts and matrix parts which

Fig. 7 Model of residual stress distribution in FRP specimen. (a) side view of specimen, (b) optical path length in FRP specimen, l_m : for matrix, l_y : for resin in yarn, (c) residual stress distribution in FRP specimen(m: for matrix, y: for yarn).

except the yarn parts. Fig.7 shows the schematic side view of specimen and the residual stress distribution obtained by the photoelastic observation. Fig.7-(b) shows both light path lengths of the matrix parts which except the yarn parts and of the resin parts in the yarn. And the residual stress in the matrix parts is different from that of resin parts in the yarn. Consequently Fig.7-(c) shows the total residual stress distribution model for the photoelastic observation in the specimen. The residual stress value (σ_{0m} and σ_{0y}) and the material property are shown in Table 2 and these values are measured with the Babinet's compensator.

1) Map of the isochromatic line (n=1)

The theoretical results of isochromatic lines for matrix are shown in Fig.8. Both results for isotropic and orthotropic materials show a good coincident to each other. Fig.9 shows the irregularity of isochromatic line between matrix parts and yarn parts. Fig.8 and Fig.9 well explain the experimental results.

		n = 1	n = 2	n = 3	n = 4	n = 6
σ_{0m}	MPa	2.16	5.18	7.58	9.76	15.9
σ_{0y}	MPa	0	0.37	0.75	1.18	2.30
E_1	GPa	3.92	4.88	5.72	5.94	7.22
E_2	GPa	3.80	4.22	4.39	4.59	4.84
G_{12}	GPa	1.29	1.30	1.35	1.36	1.48
ν_{12}	—	0.341	0.418	0.380	0.398	0.375

Table 2 Material property of multilayer specimen.
n: number of yarn.

Fig. 8 Map of isochromatic lines(for matrix).

(a) isotropic materials, (b) orthotropic materials, load: P=882N, residual stress: $\sigma_0 = 2.16$ MPa.

Fig. 9 Map of isochromatic lines(for FRP model).

load: P=882N, residual stress: $\sigma_{0m} = 2.16$ MPa(for matrix), $\sigma_{0y} = 0$ (for the center of yarn).

The point C is the intersection of two envelope of isochromatic lines for matrix and yarn parts and OA is the line perpendicular to the yarn from the point O (Fig.10). The angle $\beta (= \angle COA)$ is not influenced very much by the alteration of both wedge angle and the inclination angle of yarn. Since the experimental results are almost similar to the theoretical results, all points on the irregular shaped isochromatic line show the same degree value in the discrepancy of two principal strains.

Fig. 11 Map of isoclinic lines. (a) isotropic materials, (b) Orthotropic materials, load: $P=294N$, residual stress: $\sigma_0=2.16MPa$.

Fig. 10 Relation between angle and wedge angle.

The map in the figure shows the envelope of isochromatic lines for both matrix and yarn. Dotted line shows the calculation value of analysis.

2) Map of the isocliniclines ($n=1$)

The theoretical results which obtained for the both material properties, isotropic and orthotropic, are shown in Fig.11 and have a good agreement to the experimental results. The movement of the singular point for the indenting load is strongly affected by the inclination angle of yarn as shown in Fig.12 and the theoretical results for both inclination angles of yarn, $\alpha = 60^\circ$ and $\alpha = 30^\circ$, were found to be coincident with the experimental results.

3) Application for multilayer of unidirectional glass fiber reinforced plastics ($n > 1$)

For one ply specimen the theoretical results well explain the experimental results, so next we discuss how to apply this analysis for multilayer unidirectional glass fiber reinforced plastics. The mechanical properties of multilayer specimen are shown in table 2, and the side view of these specomens is shown in Fig.13. Since each yarn is arranged independently in the specimen, it is considered that the distribution of residual stress in the matrix part is independent each specimen. The residual stress in the matrix part which excepts the yarn parts is not dependent on the number of yarn.

The both experimental and theoretical results are shown in Fig.14. If the residual stress is larger than the stress value corresponding to the one fringe value, the isochromatic pattern differs from that of one ply specimen. The theoretical results well explain the experimental results.

Fig. 12 Movement of singular point. (a) experimental result, (b) theoretical result, ΔL : distance between singular point and loading point.

Fig. 13 The side view of multilayer specimen.

Fig. 14 Isochromatic lines of both experimental and theoretical results for multilayer specimen.
 load: $P=882N$, n : number of yarn.

CONCLUSION

The phenomena of the deformation of unidirectional glass fiber reinforced plastic materials at the wedge indentation were studied by means of photoelastic method. The photoelastic fringe patterns are calculated by using the residual stress distribution in the specimen. The main results obtained are as follow:

- 1) The photoelastic fringe was strongly affected by the inclination angle of yarn to the side of rectangular specimen, while not affected by the shape of wedge indenter in the range of small indenting depth. The isochromatic fringe shows the irregularity between yarn and matrix parts, otherwise on the map of isoclinic lines the singular point appears in the matrix parts.
- 2) On the theoretical analysis assuming that the residual stress exists in the specimen instead of the existence of yarn, the theoretical results have a good agreement to the experimental results.
- 3) For the multilayer unidirectional glass fiber reinforced plastic specimen (which distance between yarns keeps constant), if both the residual stress distribution and the matrix property were able to get by the experiment or the law of mixture, the photoelastic fringe patterns are easily calculated by using this analysis.

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